

Factor Analysis of Reliability on Mechanical Properties of CFRP

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the behavior of crack propagate to the fiber direction in the failure of CFRP laminates were examined by handling of mechanical fracture. Specially, we pay attention to the difference of behavior by crack propagate to interlaminar and intralaminar. As a result, toughening the matrix resin was proved to increase the interlaminar and the intralaminar toughness, and can be yield a improvement of the reliability of CFRP and shift the strength to higher values. but the degree of improvement depends on the fiber and the matrix resin.

1. INTRODUCTION

Unidirectional CFRP laminates have many good properties however it is one problem on practical use that toughness is low, Specially, in case of composite by which epoxy system resin is assumed to be matrix, when crack progresses to the fiber direction, fracture toughness is low as compared with metal. Therefore the behavior of crack progresses in fiber direction is an important factor to handle composite fracture mechanical. Since the Griffith's brittle fracture theory, it is found that the fracture mechanics as for an engineering system which quantitatively handle the strength of an object with crack, repaidly developed¹⁾. In order to handle the fracture behavior of brittle composite, the examination with the fracture mechanics is nessary. From the point of reliability design in metal material, the general idea of fracture mechanics introduced damage tolerant design is used as the important technique in order to assure reliability and safety

Table 1 Mechanical properties of neat resins

Resin	Tensile strength	Ultimate strain	Elastic modulus	Fracture toughness	
	(MPa)	(%)	(GPa)	K _{1c} (MPa√m)	G _{1c} (N/m)
#3601	60.8	2.0	3.8	0.56	73
#3631	90.0	4.7	3.3	0.67	120

of the structure parts. According with the extension of the application in main structure parts, the damage tolerance become important and the crack propagation of fatigue has been the subject of several studies^{2),3)}. However, the fracture process of composite are complexly and no arrived to the fully elucidation is the present, so the basic matter like the static crack progress process must be examined.

In this paper, the behavior of crack propagate to the fiber direction in the failure of CFRP laminates were examined by handling of mechanical fracture. Specially, we pay attention to the difference of behavior by crack propagates to the interlaminar and the intralaminar⁴⁾. Moreover, we used the data which were obtained from the reliability evaluation of tensile properties of unidirectional CFRP laminates⁵⁾ in order to examine the factors of variability and have the information concerning reliability improvement.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

CFRP used in this experiment is unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy laminate. Two types of PAN based carbon fibers, T300 and T800, are used. As for the matrix, two type of epoxy resin systems are used, which are 177°C cure types of #3601 and #3631. The #3601 is a conventional brittle resin system based on glycidylamino epoxy resin and DDS. The #3631 is modified to be tougher than the #3601. The properties of neat resins are shown in Table 1. With each of these two matrix systems and both types of fibers, four different prepregs were prepared.

In order to characterize the mechanical properties of composites, several different tests were conducted. These include the center cracked plate tension (CCT) test and the double cantilever beam (DCB) test to determine the intralaminar fracture toughness and the interlaminar fracture toughness of a composite. Scanning electron microscopy was used to examine the fracture of specimen and characterize the fracture mechanisms.

Mode I fracture toughness experiment of intralaminar and interlaminar were performed. Intralaminar fracture toughness of composites was measured by CCT test and interlaminar fracture toughness of composites was measured by DCB test. The configuration of CCT and DCB specimens are shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 Geometry of fracture toughness test specimens.

2-1 INTRALAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

In case of CCT test, critical stress concentration coefficient of Mold I, K_{IC} is given by

$$K_{IC} = \sigma_C \cdot \sqrt{\pi a_0} \cdot F(a/w) \quad (1)$$

where a_0 is initial crack length, W is the width of specimen, σ_C is critical loading stress and $F(a/w)$ is the correction term. In this paper, we used Tada's expression and made $\xi = a/W$ therefore

$$F(\xi) = (1 - 0.0025\xi^2 + 0.06\xi^4) \cdot \sqrt{\text{Sec}(\pi\xi/2)} \quad (2)$$

In case of this function, the error is 0.1% in $0 < \xi < 1$ region. The critical stress was obtained by the way of the loading stress in the time of specimen broken, because of specimen's brittle fracture was happened in the linear elastic region.

2-2 INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The straight-sided DCB specimen, developed by Kageyama^{6,7)} and Hojo⁸⁾, was utilized to measure the mode I interlaminar fracture toughness of composite materials in this research. To prepare DCB specimens, a teflon film was inserted into the midplane of each laminate to serve as a crack initiator and a pair of steel hinges were joined onto the specimens for attachment to an Instron universal testing machine. The value of the interlaminar fracture toughness, G_I was calculated using Kageyama's analytical compliance method. That is,

$$G_I = P^2 / 2b \cdot d\lambda / da \quad (3)$$

where P is the load, b is the width of specimen, a is the crack length and λ is the compliance. In this paper, compliance λ was obtained by next expression⁹⁾

$$a/H = A_1 \cdot \lambda^{1/3} + A_0 \quad (4)$$

where a is the crack length, H is the half length of specimen thickness and parameter A_0 and A_1 are obtained by experiment results

Table.2 Intralaminar fracture toughness of unidirectional composites.

Reinforcing fibers / Matrix resins	Fracture Toughness	
	K _{1c} (MPa \sqrt{m})	G _{1c} (N/m)
T300/#3601	1.6	210
T300/#3631	1.7	240
T800/#3601	1.4	150
T800/#3631	1.5	200

T300/#3601

T300/#3631

T800/#3601

T800/#3631

Fig.2 The SEM micrograph for the intralaminar fracture surface of CCT specimens.

with self-squares method. Make crack length normalized, then from equation (4) we can get

$$d\lambda/da = (3 \cdot \lambda^{2/3}) / (A_1 \cdot H) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3 Relationship between normalized crack length and energy release rate of interlaminar specimens.

so the value of interlaminar fracture toughness, G_I become

$$G_I = (3 \cdot P^2 \cdot \lambda^{2/3}) / (2 \cdot A_1 \cdot b \cdot H) \quad (6)$$

3. RESULTS

3-1 INTRALAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The results of intralaminar fracture toughness are listed in Table 2. The intralaminar fracture toughness of specimens which used #3631 resin, is higher than #3601 specimen. It is thought because the toughening the matrix resin can increase the delamination resistance, so the intralaminar fracture toughness of composite can be rise by toughening the matrix resin. Moreover, it is admitted that the intralaminar fracture toughness of T300 specimens are higher than T800 specimens. Presented in Fig 2 are the SEM micrograph for the fracture surface of specimens. Different phenomena were seen from the fracture surface, the matrix fracture was observed in the T300 specimens, the other way, in case of T800 specimens, the interfacial debonding can be easily observed.

Table.3 Interlaminar fracture toughness of unidirectional composites.

Reinforcing fibers / Matrix resins	Fracture Toughness	
	K _{1c} (MPa \sqrt{m})	G _{1c} (N/m)
T300/#3601	1.0	90
T300/#3631	1.3	160
T800/#3601	1.0	80
T800/#3631	1.4	170

3-2 INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The relation between normalized crack length and energy release rate of composites is shown in Fig 3. The interlaminar fracture toughness of T300 specimens were independent on the crack growth, nearly a constant. On the other hand, the interlaminar fracture toughness of T800 specimens were increase with the crack growth, it is thought that is the influence of bridging fiber due to the crack propagation. In case of T300 specimens, the crack propagate in the resin excessive layer of interlaminar, because the T300 specimens have a higher interfacial bonding. however, the crack shifts to the interface and causes fiber bridging in the T800 specimens. this is due to the poor interfacial bonding between the T800 fiber and the epoxy resin.

The results of interlaminar fracture toughness is listed in Table 3, shown that the toughening of matrix resin is the key to improving the interlaminar fracture toughness.

4. DISCUSSION

Longitudinal properties, mean value of tensile strength and coefficient of variation of tensile strength, of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced composites are shown in Fig 4. that mean value of tensile strength of T800 specimens are higher than T300 specimens because the mainly affect factor of tensile strength on-axes is the reinforced fiber. If we compare in the specimens which have same reinforced fiber then we can find the influence of matrix resin. that is the tensile strength of specimens, which used toughed resin #3631, are higher than those specimens which used brittle resin #3601.

Concerning coefficient of variation of longitudinal tensile strength, in case of T300 specimens, as shown in Fig 4, there is a distinct improvement for the T300/#3631 specimen. it is admitted that coefficient of variation of longitudinal tensile strength of CFRP was improved by used the toughed resin #3631. However, in the case of T800 specimens, it is found that the difference of coefficient of variation of longitudinal tensile strength between T800/#3601 and T800/#3631

Fig.4 Mean value of longitudinal tensile strength and coefficient of variation of longitudinal tensile strength.

Fig.5 Mean value of transverse tensile strength and coefficient of variation of transverse tensile strength.

specimen is considerably small. it is considered that the difference in longitudinal properties between T300 and T800 specimens is caused by the magnitude of fiber fracture energy; that is to say, the fiber fracture energy in the T800 specimens is so large that the influence of matrix toughness on the fracture mode can be ignored, while the influence in the T300 specimens can not be ignored.

Fig.6 Comparison between interlaminar energy release rate and intralaminar energy release rate.

These results indicate that toughening the matrix resin can yield a pronounced improvement of the reliability of CFRP and shift of the strength to higher values, but the degree of improvement depends on the combination of fiber and matrix.

On the other way, coefficient of variation of transverse tensile strength and mean value of transverse tensile strength of four types unidirectional CFRP are shown in Fig 5. Because the mainly affect factor of transverse tensile strength is matrix resin, so it is admitted that mean value of transverse tensile strength of specimens can be rise by used the toughed resin #3631.

The estimation results are shown in Fig 6, the broken line is the toughness of the neat resin. Toughening the matrix resin was proved to improve the intralaminar and the interlaminar fracture toughness. The crack in the interlaminar was observed to propagate in the resin excessive layer which does not exist bridging fiber. but in case of crack propagated in the intralaminar direction, it is found that the bridging fiber exist in the crack propagation direction. Therefore, it is thought that the presence of a reinforced fiber interference is the important cause of the difference of interlaminar and intralaminar fracture toughness of composites.

Concerning coefficient of variation of transverse tensile strength, obviously, the difference between the T300/#3601 and the T300/#3631 was observed. It is admitted that coefficient of variation of transverse tensile strength was improved by using the toughened resin #3631. In case of T800 specimens, it is found that the difference of coefficient of variation of transverse tensile strength between T800/#3601 and T800/#3631 specimen is considerably small. It is considered because the fracture mode of the T300 specimens shown matrix fracture so using the toughened resin can obstruct the micro fracture progress within the composites and also can suppress the brittle fracture of composites. On the other hand, in case of T800 specimens, the influence of matrix fracture toughness is considerably small because the fracture mode shown interfacial debonding. Therefore, the difference of coefficient of variation of transverse tensile strength between T800/#3601 and T800/#3631 specimens can be ignored.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be reached from the current research:

1. The toughness of resin #3631 is higher than the resin #3601 and influence on the toughness of the unidirectional composites.
2. The crack propagates in the resin excessive layer of interlaminar of the T300 specimen, otherwise, in case of the T800 specimen, the crack shifts to the interface and causes the fiber bridging.
3. The presence of the interference of a reinforced fiber is the cause of the difference of crack propagation behavior in intralaminar and interlaminar.
4. Toughening the matrix resin was proved to increase the interlaminar and the intralaminar toughness of composites.
5. Toughening the matrix resin yields an improvement of the reliability of CFRP and shifts the tensile strength to higher values, but the degree of improvement depends on the combination of the fiber and the matrix resin.

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